

PHRASEOLOGY AND THE PROBLEM OF PHRASEOLOGISMS

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Abstract: *In this article, we will talk about phraseology in English and the problem of translation in them, as well as the importance of phraseology in language learning. So, through this article, we can provide enough information to people who want to learn idioms and phraseology. Because this field is the least researched and researched among other fields.*

Key words: *combinations, phraseology, philology, proverbs, idioms, morphology, sarcasm.*

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INTRODUCTION: Knowing a language is an asset. A person who knows a language knows the world, never less it won't happen. Our ancestors were like that, it's in our blood. We need to awaken such aspiration in our youth, - said Shavkat Mirziyoyev. Doing research on foreign languages, language teaching methodology improvement, it is noted that classes in the boarding school should be conducted on this basis done. Philology of English, German, French, Russian, Arabic, Chinese, Korean languages at school is taught. Uzbekistan State University of World Languages, Tashkent State Institute of Oriental Studies, Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and Literature cooperation will be established. Foreign volunteers are also involved in the teaching process.

Due to the complexity of the nature of phraseological units, it has not been implemented until now formation of phraseological units mainly in increased research works their meaningfulness, the essence of meaning after learning the ways not fully researched from the linguistic point of view. English in research work the semantic-structural features of phraseologisms are considered in detail and how they are reflected in dictionaries.

MATERIALS AND DISCUSSION: Phraseological units are part of the language consideration as an integral part of phraseology is general and specific requires a thorough study of its laws. Phraseological units analysis of semantic stylistic features, as everyone knows, is very broad is a comprehensive field. Studying this issue in conjunction with dictionaries the exit issue has not been positively resolved so far. Some studies in the field of sociolinguistics, general linguistics works are also devoted to this issue, but these studies are usually general has a character, phraseological materials are rarely referred to. The vocabulary of any language is not only about creating new words, maybe, because of expressions, stable word combinations, both in terms of quantity and quality becomes richer in terms of with the "world" with such stable compounds the science involved is the science of phraseology. Phraseology is the study of phrases and this term was used by E.D. Polivanov in

1928: I refer to morphology Syntax is related to lexis to use the term "phraseology" as a special science dealing with relation. [2.67]

In fact, phraseology has been part of world linguistics for the past half century became the center of attention, as a result of a series of monographic scientific researches object was determined, research methods were developed, and this science is linguistics has formed its place among other fields. Nowadays, this term is two is used in the meaning.

1. The total number of phraseological combinations in the language;
2. The field, science, which studies fixed expressions. [1.98]

In recent years, many languages have been used on the basis of materials as a result of large-scale phraseological research, phraseologisms are as follows is being described. Forming phraseology the components does not have a wholeness of meaning, they are only aspects of form and sound is similar to the word with. Phraseology of the components that make them up a sign with a stable meaning, more emotional expressiveness, represents action. That is why the phraseological meaning is lexical differs from the meaning in several ways. Most of the phraseologisms identity does not exist, that is, what this phraseology is expressing meaning cannot be replaced by one word and this meaning is a free word can only be explained by the combination. The scientific classification of fixed expressions in languages is, first of all, should consist of organizing the terms given to phraseology. In linguistics, there are various terms used to express fixed word combinations is being used. This is the nature of these fixed phrases is occurring due to its complexity. They are semantic, structural and functional are considered complex in terms of structure, stylistic, semantic, complex, syntactic function of speech and other principles classified based on as one of the traditional classification methods classification based on the structural-semantic principle is recognized. [3.102]

According to him stable phrases, pairs of words, idioms, wise words (aphorisms), divided into proverbs. Everyone knows that every language has a paremiology, that is, a stable word to imagine the field of study of combinations without proverbs and proverbs difficult. In linguistics, the concepts of proverb are given different definitions. Proverbs and sayings are sources of emotional images of the language. That is, proverbs are the advice of the people, spiritual and moral conclusions, the national spirit of the people is the opposite. The proverb has a very deep social meaning. [4.213]

That's why some proverbs it can illuminate the content of an entire work. Proverbial sadness - people's sadness, proverbial anger - people's anger, proverb laughter means people's laughter and proverbial irony means people's irony. There is no nation that did not use it, no language that did not create a proverb. There are proverbs that a sweet advises, teaches wisdom, is brave and heroic invites to be; he will tell your fault to your lazy face, bribe taker, slanderer, liar, thief, swindler, hypocrite, flatterer, flatterer, punishes a crook: sting with bitter words does, gives a mixture of complaint and sarcasm. As the proverb is born day by day among the people, as a saying of fathers and grandfathers, it is passed down from generation to generation. People are very careful about this heritage that he keeps it like the apple of an eye. Each proverb has its meaning, form, and stylistic function has its own characteristics. But still, in all proverbs, the people wisdom lies. Proverb tried in marriage, known good, complete, general meaning, it is folk wisdom in a concise form them.

CONCLUSION: In general, before teaching translation in schools, translation is in one language, we understand that the thought that appeared will be transferred to the second language. This is different a common understanding has emerged between the peoples who speak the language. Thus translation develops the ability to think in both languages. The fixed phrases in the language reflect the entire history and way of life of these people, therefore writers often refer to them. Fixed phrases are a work of art is an alternative methodical tool to make the language juicy and impressive. Figuratively so to speak, what an eye is to a ring, so to the speech of a proverbial speaker, such power gives vitality to the image of the writer in some works proverbs given as epigraphs clearly express the idea and purpose of this work serves to stand.

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